

Mallinātha or Lakṣmī? A Re-Identification of a Jaina Icon utilizing Sanskrit Texts dealing with Iconography

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Introduction

The Indian subcontinent is home to a rich heritage of religious and cultural artefacts, including idols of deities that are frequently unearthed through excavation or other means. However, the lack of inscriptions on many of these idols can make it challenging to accurately identify the deity they represent. In such cases, the use of texts containing attributes of the deities can prove to be a valuable resource in correctly identifying the deity and understanding the religio-cultural history of the region.

Identification of deities is important for two main reasons. Firstly, it allows for a better understanding of the evolution of iconography, which is important in understanding how the deity has been represented over the time. Secondly, it enables us to understand the religio-cultural history of a particular region, providing insights into the beliefs, practices, and customs of the people who lived there.

In this paper, we focus on the identification of a Jaina idol using various Sanskrit texts on iconography. Specifically, we draw upon the "*Bṛhatsamhitā*" (6th Cent. C.E.), "*Mānasāra*" (6th Cent. C.E.), "*Mayamatam*," "*Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa*" (15th Cent. C.E.), and "*Śilparatna*" (16th Cent. C.E.) to accurately identify the deity represented by the idol.

Case

The image under investigation (Image 1) is claimed to be of *Tīrthankara Mallinātha*. It is located at the Shri Sambhavnath Jain Temple in Sambhavnath's Khadki, Opp. Aambli Pol, Javeriwad, Ahmedabad. Based on the stylistic features of the idol, it can be inferred that the idol dates back to the Solanki/Caulukya period¹, specifically the 11th to 13th century C.E.

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The image of the idol was first circulated on the Facebook page of Devlok Jinalaya Palitana, and was subsequently shared by Arpit Shah, a professional architect based in Kolkata, on his personal website². Neither Mr. Shah nor the Devlok Jinalaya page have taken any initiative to correctly identify the idol.

It has been reported in *Śvetāmbara* literature that *Mallinātha*, the 19th *Tīrthaṅkara*, is said to be a female. Consequently, she is regarded as the only female *Tīrthaṅkara* of this particular time cycle. Although female depictions of the *Tīrthaṅkara Mallinātha* are rare, some idols have been discovered which feature the said *Tīrthaṅkara* in female form, characterized by prominent breasts and braided hair³. At present, the tradition of depicting *Mallinātha* in female form appears to be lost, although a handful of such idols have been discovered and are actively worshipped.

Problem

The present study aims to demonstrate that the idol in question cannot be identified as that of *Tīrthaṅkara Mallinātha* based on several grounds. Firstly, the idol possesses four hands, a feature not observed in any *Tīrthaṅkara* idols. Although the existence of idols of *Tīrthaṅkara Candra* with seven heads has been recorded, such instances are exceedingly rare⁴. Secondly, the idol is adorned with lotus buds, and their stems are present in the upper two hands. Thirdly, the idol lacks the presence of the *Śrīvatsa* symbol on the chest, a customary symbol associated with *Tīrthaṅkara* idols. Fourthly, two elephants are depicted above the upper two hands of the sculpture.

Texts

i) About *Tīrthaṅkara* – Analysis of relevant texts dealing with the iconography of *Tīrthaṅkara*, such as *Bṛhatsamhitā*⁵, *Mānasāra*⁶, and *Mayamatam*⁷, reveals that *Tīrthaṅkara* idols should have two hands, with the posture being either lotus or standing straight. The presence of ornaments is discouraged, and the *Śrīvatsa* symbol on the chest is mandatory. The idol should be depicted naked with a shaved head. Therefore, based on the aforementioned discrepancies, it is evident that the idol in question cannot be identified as that of *Tīrthaṅkara Mallinātha*.

ii) About *Lakṣmi* – The present discourse concerns *Lakṣmi* and her iconographic features, as elucidated in several ancient texts, including the *Mayamatam*⁸, *Mānasāra*⁹, *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa*¹⁰, and *Śilparatna*¹¹. These texts describe the prominent features of *Lakṣmī's* iconography, which include the depiction of the goddess holding a lotus in her hands, accompanied by two elephants who are shown pouring water over her. Additionally, the idols of *Lakṣmī* are embellished with various ornaments, and typically feature either two or four hands. These aforementioned characteristics are commonly observed in depictions of *Gajalakṣmī*. The *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa* specifically highlights the inclusion of the stem of the lotus in the iconography of *Lakṣmī*.

Correct Identification

The creation of a sculpture involves a degree of artistic freedom, which often deviates from the literal depiction of textual descriptions. Consequently, our examined idol displays some level of erosion, resulting in the obscurity of certain features. Upon closer inspection, however, two small elephants are visible on either side of the idol's head. The idol is well-ornamented. Lotus stems with buds are suspended from the idol's upper hands, while two female attendants are situated adjacent to the sculpture. The earrings, shaped like *Makara*, are also noticeable. Another similar idol, identified as a *Yoga Lakṣmī* rather than the *Tīrthāṅkara Mallinātha*, is present in the Jain temple of Mt. Abu (Image 2). These attributes do not match with the *Tīrthāṅkara* description.

Upon closer examination, it becomes apparent that the aforementioned idol was not created for the purpose of active worship, but rather for ornamental purposes within the temple. Analysis of the idol's sides indicates that it formed a constituent element of a *Devakoṣṭha* located outside of the temple, specifically above the *Gavākṣa* or *Candrāvalokana* (as exemplified by image no. 3).

Conclusion

The identification of the deity represented by an idol holds significant importance. Upon examining the attributes and comparable instances, it has been established that the idol under scrutiny does not pertain to *Tīrthāṅkara Mallinātha* but rather belongs to goddess *Lakṣmī*. This case study underscores the crucial role of utilizing relevant texts in accurately identifying deities and comprehending the transformation of iconography throughout history.

References

1. (1954) *Political History of Northern India from Jain Sources (C.650 A.D. to 1300 A.D.)*, Pp. 212,.
2. Shah, Arpit (2017) 'Ancient Idols of Lord Mallinath worshipped in female form'.
<https://www.storiesbyarpit.com/2017/12/ancient-idols-of-lord-mallinath.html>
3. (2010). *Encyclopaedia of Jaina Studies*, Vol. I, Pp. 277,
4. Victoria & Albert Museum record link: <https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O60349/sculpture-unknown/>
5. *ājānulambabāhuḥ śrīvatsāṅkaḥ praśāntamūrtiśca | digvāsāstaruṇo rūpavāṁśca kāryo'rhatam devaḥ ||* - *Bṛhatsaṁhitā* LVIII: 45.
6. *sthāvaram jaṅgamam caiva lakṣaṇam vakṣyate'dhunā | Dvibhujam ca dvinetram ca muṇḍatāram ca śīrṣakam || rjushānakasaṁyuktam tathā cāsanameva ca | asaṅghri rju(jvā)kāram syāllambahastadvayam yathā || āsanam ca dvipāḍau ca padmāsanam tu saṁyutam | rjukam ca rjo(ju)bhāvam yogam tatparamānta(tma)kam ||* - *Mānasāra* LV: 36 - 38.
Nirābharaṇasarvāṅgam manoharam | sama(rva)vakṣaḥsthale hemavarṇam śrīvatsalāñcanam || - *Mānasāra* LV:46.
7. *Sthānakamāsanamuktam sirṁhapadmāsanānvitam ||* - *Mayamatam* 36: 284 (B).
Śeṣam pūrvavaduddiṣṭam yuktyā rūpam nirambaram || - *Mayamatam* 36:286 (A).
Pārvabāhulatāratnam tattadvarṇam dvibāhukaḥ || - *Mayamatam* 36: 287(A).
Tyaktābharaṇamūrdhvajam | - *Mayamatam* 36: 282(A).
Note: *Śeṣam pūrvavaduddiṣṭam...* | 36:286(A) of *Mayamatam* points towards the description which one can find earlier dealing with the iconography of Buddha. The 36: 282(A) states that the idol should not have any ornaments.
8. *Lakṣmīḥ padmāsanāsīnā dvibhujā kāñcanaprabhā ||* - *Mayamatam* 36: 247(B).
Hemaratojvalam nakrakuṇḍalam śaṅkha [-kuṇḍalam] || - *Mayamatam* 36: 248(A).
Mekhalā kaṣīṣūtram ca sarvābharaṇabhūṣitā || - *Mayamatam* 36: 251(B).
Cāmaravyagrahaste ca tatpārśve tu striyāvubhe | - *Mayamatam* 36:252(B).
Snayantau kumbhastau hastinau ca pradarsayet | atha gehārcanāyogyā caturbāhusamanvitā || - *Mayamatam* 36: 253.
9. *Śeṣam tu pūrvavatkuryād devīm(vi) pārśve viśeṣataḥ | airāvataadvayoś(yam) caiva kuryādārāda(dha)yetsudhiḥ ||* - *Mānasāra* LIV: 33.
Caturbhujam trinetrām ca ... | - *Mānasāra* LIV: 20(A).
Pīnonnatastanatātām phāle bhramarakānvitām | - *Mānasāra* LIV: 23(B).
Makaram kuṇḍalam vāpi karṇayoḥ svarṇadāmayuk | - *Mānasāra* LIV: 24(B).
10. *dvivyāmbujakarā kāryā sarvābharaṇabhūṣitā |* - *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa* 8: 105(A).
Prathamā caturbhujā kāryā devī simhāsane śubhā | - *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa* 8: 106(A).
Bṛhannālam kare kāryam tasyādhaḥ kamalam śubham | - *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa* 8: 108(A).
Āvarjitaghaṭam kāryam tatpṛṣṭham ca karadvayam | - *Devatāmurtiprakaraṇa* 8:110(A).
11. *Muktāgauraiścaturbhirdvipapatibhiratho puṣkarodyadghaṭasyā-nniryadratnābhīṣiktā karakamalalasaṭpadmayugmābhayeṣṭā | nānākalpābhīrāmā drutakanakanibhā raktapaṅkeruhasṭhā ramyāṅgī suprasannā vitaratu vipulam santatam śrīḥ śriyam vaḥ ||* - *Śilparatna* 24: 9.
Śbhrebhadvayapuṣkareritaghataghaṭaścyotadvīśuddhodakaiḥ snāyantīmatihrdyarūpavibhavām nīlollasatkuntalām | śubhrākalpaviśeṣavibhramarasāmuttaptahemaprabhām vande bāhuyugaprasaktakamalām devīm sarojāsānām || - *Śilparatna* 24:10.

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Plates

Image 1

Image 2 Lakṣmī (c. 1150 C.E.), southern bay ceiling, Vimalavasahī, Mt. Abu.

Source: Encyclopaedia of Jaina studies Vol.I.

Image 3 A type of Devakoṣṭha, Ranakpur. Source: wikimediacommons